

Strategy for HPC Integration in WLCG/HEP

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Executive Summary

High-Energy Physics (HEP), and particularly the sector supported by the WLCG Collaboration at the LHC experiments, is entering a new era of data-intensive research. This shift is driven by the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) that will generate exabyte-scale datasets each year. Fully realizing the physics potential of this massive volume of data will require a significant increase of resources. High Performance Computing (HPC) centers are crucial partners in this effort, offering either pledged resources or for providing additional opportunistic resources that enhance the physics output. Integrating HPC systems into HEP workflows offers transformative benefits, like expanding computational power, accelerating simulations, and enabling more sophisticated AI/ML algorithms. However, realizing these benefits demands a concerted effort to address technical, organizational, and policy-related barriers.

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Technical Challenges

1. **Interfaces, Authorization and Authentication, and Heterogeneity:** HPC sites vary center-by-center in their hardware, software, and policies. Standard interfaces and protocols are needed for seamless access, efficient job scheduling, and data transfers. The distributed LHC computing is based on the WLCG Trust model, in which access is granted to users via membership in a recognized Virtual Organization (VO), externally defined. A federated, standards-based approach to the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) is needed to enable a global collaboration.
2. **Software and Architectures:** HEP codebases, traditionally optimized for x86_64 CPUs, require modernization to run efficiently on different architectures and/or on GPUs and other accelerators, which are increasingly used at HPC sites. Portable parallelization strategies and updated programming models are essential to keep pace with evolving hardware. The code modernisation process is not expected to cover all the relevant workflows. Therefore, the availability of sizable CPU resources will likely remain a requirement in the medium to long term.
3. **Data Management and Networking:** Efficient, high-throughput data pipelines are critical. HEP workloads depend on large volumes of data both within and outside HPC centers, necessitating robust networking (including links with NRENs), on-site caching solutions and data management protocols to ensure integrity in distributed workflows.
4. **Workflows:** From real-time calibration to long-term campaign simulations, HEP workflows must be optimized for HPC architectures, data flows, and access policies to exploit the scale and performance offered by modern supercomputers. Sophisticated workflow orchestration systems must be developed that are able to dynamically allocate and adjust resources across HPC and WLCG. Another dimension is the difference between organized processing campaigns (“production”) and chaotic end-user “analysis” activities. Ideally both should be supported at the HPC centers, but directing only specific workflows (for example those more computing intensive) to HPC sites is a solution, at least initially -- at the cost of a potentially less efficient resource utilization.
5. **AI/ML Integration:** Machine Learning and AI are increasingly critical in HEP — improving simulation, data selection, and analysis. While current HEP-specific models typically require fewer resources than Large Language Models (LLMs), the interest in Foundation Models and advanced techniques like AutoML is steadily growing, implying a need for scalable, AI-centric infrastructure, where HPC centers excel.

Policy and Governance Considerations

- **Provisioning and Accounting:** The long-term nature of HEP programs often conflicts with typical annual HPC allocation cycles or sudden and unplanned availability of large-scale resources, which impedes efficient resource planning.
- **Strategic Access:** Recognizing HEP as a strategic science initiative—particularly in Europe — can help secure multi-year allocations of HPC resources. This approach would enable more ambitious projects and ensure HPC sites consistently contribute to HEP’s global scientific mission.
- **Collaboration mechanisms:** Establishing coordination and collaboration mechanisms between the organizations managing HPC resources and the WLCG is essential to effectively carry out the integration project.
- **(Co-)Design:** HPC centers are often designed with their traditional stakeholders—such as Lattice QCD, climate science, chemistry, and astrophysics—in mind. Currently, HEP projects typically gain access only after these systems have been deployed and validated, leaving minimal room for HEP to influence design decisions. As a result, HEP teams often need to develop workarounds or run sub-optimally for aspects like node design, networking, external routing, and access policies. Involving HEP representatives early in the

design and procurement process would greatly simplify integration and ensure these systems can be leveraged more effectively for HEP research.

In summary, integrating HPC into HEP requires strategic planning, robust partnerships, and harmonization of interfaces, data workflows, and security protocols. If achieved, the payoff is substantial: harnessing exascale computing power and advanced AI capabilities to extend the physics exploitation of future particle physics experiments.

Motivation

High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments, via the WLCG Collaboration, continue to push the frontiers of scientific computing, driving innovations in data processing, analysis, and simulation. HEP experiments already produce large datasets — soon to exceed the exabyte scale annually — and the rising volume and complexity of this data demand ever-greater computational capabilities. The upcoming High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC), set to launch in 2030, has spurred aggressive R&D programs across all experiments to meet evolving requirements within constrained budgets and uncertain technology gains. These efforts focus on reworking algorithms, workflows, and data management practices to fully exploit future hardware and achieve the minimum needs of the physics program (see Figure 1.a-b-c).

Many of these planned improvements rely on yet-to-be-realized R&D programs and imply a flat budget scenario, aiming to fulfill baseline objectives. To realize the full scientific potential of the HL-LHC beyond the minimal physics program, additional resources and capabilities are needed. HPC centers are a natural candidate, with large resource deployments; among these, CPU-based systems could be used in the shortest time frame. On top of that, as HEP adopts accelerated architectures like GPUs and explores AI/ML techniques for more efficient data processing, High Performance Computing (HPC) facilities — now scaling to the exascale — can play a pivotal role. In fact, HPC resources have grown by a factor of 1000 (see Figure 1.d) since the original LHC startup, underscoring the vital contribution they can make to data-intensive sciences.

Figure 1: (a), (b), (c): ATLAS expected resource need for HL-LHC, compared with different flat budget scenarios; (d) performance evolution of HPC centers over time (in log scale).

At the intersection of HPC, AI, and data-intensive research, HEP faces challenges and opportunities, initially discussed in [1]. Strategic decisions about code optimization, workflow adaptation, and hardware design will shape the future of discovery and innovation. Efficiently managing data and I/O will be crucial in capitalizing on these evolving technologies. This document outlines the key elements necessary to develop a comprehensive strategy for integrating HPC, while identifying shared opportunities and acknowledging the unique challenges ahead. The technical issues have been identified and discussed in a series of workshops: a US-focused workshop held in January 2024 [2], a European workshop in September 2024 [3] and multi-region combined workshop held in January 2025 [4]. This white paper summarizes the technical and policy issues and identifies the next steps for a deeper integration between HPC and HEP/WLCG computing.

Technical Issues

The successful integration of HPC with HEP/WLCG hinges on addressing several interrelated technical challenges. The primary goal is the creation of standardized interfaces to streamline interactions between diverse systems and ensure that software can efficiently leverage advanced architectures like GPUs, without a dedicated center-per-center integration effort. Equally critical is the design of robust data pipelines that can handle massive throughput and adapt to HPC's often fluctuating usage patterns. Meanwhile, evolving workflows — especially those relying on machine learning — present opportunities for accelerated science and challenges in code reengineering, performance optimization, and sophisticated scheduling. The strict authorization and security requirements at HPC facilities demand meticulous planning to maintain data integrity and safeguard intellectual property, which must be integrated with the WLCG Trust model. The following sections delve deeper into these areas, outlining possible strategies to capitalize on higher performance and higher efficiency processing while also ensuring a smooth, secure, and scalable integration of HPC into the HEP computing ecosystem.

Interfaces

Each HPC center utilizes its own distinct access protocols and policies. While this variability reflects the specific needs and capabilities of each center and the heterogeneity of resources, it creates a major obstacle to integrating these resources into distributed systems like the WLCG. This lack of standardization hinders efficient data analysis for researchers.

- **Open Issues:** To use HPC resources, researchers and experiments must configure and adapt their workflows to accommodate these differences manually, a process that can be time-consuming, error-prone, inefficient, in many cases need substantial R&D, and finally in some cases simply impossible. A common set of standard interfaces and protocols, agreed with and supported by WLCG, is needed to scale the number of HPC sites participating.
- **Status:** Needs to be resolved.
- **Impact:** Without a common foundation, the ability to integrate additional HPC sites into a distributed computing environment, beyond dedicated campaigns, will continue to be labor intensive and severely limited.
- **Possible Next Steps:** Collaborate with funding agencies and existing programs like the US Department of Energy Integrated Resource Infrastructures (IRI) [5], EuroHPC JU [6] and EuroHPC Federation Platform (EFP) [7], WLCG, experiments, HPC organizations, and resource providers to document the performance, security, and technical requirements for interfaces. Trigger an effort between the interested parties to identify a minimum set of standard interfaces for HPC integration, focusing on standardization and reuse where possible.

(Co-)Design

HPC systems are procured and deployed following needs listed by the funders, which typically request optimized systems for (1) High Performance Linpack, used to rank the systems in top500.org [8], (2) a list of long standing computational-heavy workflows, including for example Lattice QCD, computational chemistry, astrophysics simulations and climate science. The systems, when procured and deployed, are not necessarily optimal for the use cases of HEP/WLCG: we have seen systems with low RAM, scarce or absent local disks, absence of IP networking, and heavily firewalled or absent geographical connections. The resulting systems can be simply unusable for HEP use cases, or, in the best cases, usable after the design and deployment of technical workarounds, varying from center to center and challenging to maintain at the HPC scale.

- **Open Issues:** HEP/WLCG processing is difficult, if not impossible, on HPC systems designed for different use cases.
- **Status:** in some cases, a-posteriori technology solutions can and have been found on a number of sites. But they are not optimized, are specific to a single center, need R&D and support.
- **Impact:** the absence of our use cases at the times of HPC tender definition and procurement impacts HEP ability to efficiently use the resources. In some cases, a technical solution is simply impossible, and centers are not utilized.
- **Possible Next Steps:**
 - HEP should be included in the design of the system requirements before the procurement phase starts. Only then can we reduce the integration effort with WLCG/HEP computing.
 - HEP should inform its funding agencies (which at times are the same funding the HPC centers) about our difficulties in integrating HPC processing in its distributed computing, and ask for direct representation at the planning phase; a positive outcome would allow a more direct utilization of HPC resources, with an increased efficiency of the scientific computing at national / regional level.

Software and Architectures

Software integration is a significant challenge when incorporating HPC resources into HEP experiments. While this is a common issue across various domains, our exceptionally large codebases make it even more critical in our case. These experiments rely on extensive codebases to process vast amounts of data and generate detailed simulations. Typically, this scientific application software comprises millions of lines of code and is developed over years or even decades by hundreds of contributors with varying levels of expertise. While the software is critical to the scientific mission, maintaining and modernizing it presents significant challenges. Historically, HEP/WLCG computing resources have been dominated by x86_64 CPUs, with most existing software optimized for this architecture.

HPC facilities are often early adopters of new technologies and increasingly rely on accelerators, such as GPUs, to enhance computational power while optimizing energy efficiency and cost. These accelerators are also integral to novel approaches and workflows, particularly those involving AI/ML techniques.

- **Open Issues:** To effectively leverage HPC facilities, it is necessary to rethink how application software is developed and maintained. One of the primary challenges lies in the fundamental differences between programming for massively parallel accelerators and traditional code executing on a single x86_64 core. Efficiently utilizing the available parallelism generally requires deep knowledge of the specific hardware architecture and the use of specialized languages and compilers to achieve optimal performance. In recent years, efforts have been made to develop portable parallelization strategies for heterogeneous architectures, which minimize the difficulties of running code across different hardware platforms and hint at some level of portability on future platforms.
- **Status:** This needs to be resolved, but it can be mitigated through portability libraries and reliance on GPU-supported applications like AI/ML algorithms.
- **Impact:** HEP applications are currently limited to x86_64 CPU architectures, which are not advancing as rapidly as other hardware platforms.
- **Possible Next Steps:**
 - Conduct a survey among experiments to assess:
 - Experiments and infrastructure readiness to use accelerated architectures like GPUs.
 - The needs and prospects for adopting portability libraries and unified programming models will be evaluated by starting with a technology survey of existing solutions (see for example, [here](#)).
 - A subset of the HEP/WLCG codes best suited for portability pilots by HL-LHC (for example, the easiest to port or the most resource hungry).
 - Establishing monitoring mechanisms to regularly assess the evolution of the GPU needs of the scientific collaborations and their impact on the computing models and on the distributed computing infrastructure

Data Management and Networking

Effective data access is crucial for most HEP applications running on HPC sites. Data handling efficiency directly impacts HEP's ability to fully utilize HPC resources, historically not designed for data intensive applications. Optimizing data access, alongside efficient software and applications, is key to maximizing HPC site utilization.

- **Open Issues:** Currently, permanent storage of large quantities of data on HPC sites is not anticipated and not desired for data ownership and preservation considerations. Instead, most available storage on HPCs is used for transient data — data imported for processing or exported after being generated at the facility.

To support these operations effectively, transient storage must scale proportionally with the compute capacity allocated to specific workloads. Additionally, storage performance must meet the demands of various workloads, particularly those involving AI applications. In this context, the network connectivity of the HPC facility is a critical factor; the ability to move data in and out of the facility at a rate that matches computing speed is essential. While general networking would be desired, good connectivity to WLCG centers is a minimal requirement. Currently, there are no common tools for the automated transfer of large amounts of data between WLCG and HPC sites. Ad-hoc solutions are being used now for such data transfer. Beyond transient storage, HPC facilities should also provide storage for configuration files and access to CVMFS (CERN Virtual Machine File System), though the future widespread use of containers may eventually alleviate the need for CVMFS there will still be the need for local caches.

- **Status:** Tolerable, given that HEP data management systems are advanced. With the development of standard and open interfaces for data transfer and access at HPC sites, the necessary scale should be achievable. Problems can arise due to HPC center policies, like the limitation of general connectivity from compute nodes.
- **Impact:** Processing, simulating, and analyzing data require access to vast amounts of data. For HPC sites to contribute, data will need to be moved efficiently.
- **Possible Next Steps:** Focus on developing WLCG-operated data challenges involving HPC sites to demonstrate the feasibility of completing workflows at the scale expected for HL-LHC. Update the WLCG-wide technical document explaining access patterns needed at sites. Engage with the HPC Federation Initiatives to co-develop the future Federated HPC data management system.

Workflows

HEP experiments require a diverse range of workflows to manage the complex tasks involved in data processing, reprocessing, Monte Carlo event generation, detector simulation, and analysis. HEP experiments have well developed workflow systems that handle the bulk of their computational needs. These systems are well developed and represent many person-years of effort. To make the HPC centers more useful to HEP, there should be a uniform mechanism(s) for integrating the HEP workflow systems into the HPC centers. These workflows are essential for interpreting experimental data, simulating particle interactions, and refining analysis techniques, and finally, maximise the physics potential of each experiment. Given the diversity of these tasks, workflows must be carefully tailored to match the computational resources available, including HPC environments. The IRI project [5] suggests a division of workflows into categories based on the type of pattern:

1. Time-Sensitive Patterns

These workflows require rapid processing and immediate responsiveness, often necessitating real-time data access and quick turnaround times. Examples of time-sensitive HEP workflows include:

- **Event Scouting:** Quickly analyzing subsets of data to identify interesting events that may require further, more detailed analysis.
- **ML Training and Tuning:** Rapidly iterating over AI/ML models, adjusting parameters to improve performance in real-time applications.
- **Data Quality Monitoring:** Test data for unexpected behavior, for example incorrect detector calibration or functioning, trigger decisions, and accelerator settings.

2. Data-Integration-Intensive Patterns

Workflows in this category involve the processing and integration of large, complex datasets from multiple sources. These workflows are crucial for the reduction, analysis, and interpretation of data, which are core activities in the experiments:

- **Detector Calibration:** Ensuring that detector systems are accurately calibrated in near real-time to maintain data quality.
- **Data Reduction:** Filtering and condensing large volumes of raw data into manageable datasets for further analysis steps.
- **Data Analysis:** Integrating and analyzing datasets to extract meaningful physics results, often involving complex statistical methods and cross-referencing with auxiliary data.

3. Long-Term Campaign Patterns

HEP experimental data is acquired and simulated over the course of many years. There is a big upfront computing need, described in the following bullets, that is then turned into 100s of publications per year on a wide variety of topics. As described later, HPCs without long term campaign policies are not a good fit for HEP computing needs.

- **Event Generation:** Simulating particle collisions to produce synthetic datasets that mimic real experimental conditions.
 - **Detector Simulation:** Modeling the behavior of particles as they pass through detectors, which can be performed with detailed ("FullSim") or parameterized ("FastSim") approaches.
 - **Event Reconstruction:** Interpreting low-level detector signals to identify and characterize physics objects, is a critical step in transforming raw data into scientifically useful information. This includes the reprocessing of the same data with improved algorithms.
 - **Data Derivation:** Reducing data to create more refined analysis-ready datasets, for example, incorporating data cleaning, feature extraction, and other preprocessing steps.
 - **End-to-End Processing:** Sequentially executing the full chain of workflows, from event generation to final data derivation or analysis, ensuring continuity and consistency across the entire process to minimise data flows to and from the HPC".
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- **Open Issues:** There are a very limited number of HEP workflows that have been entirely optimized for the HPC resources including HPC architectures, data flows, and authorization infrastructures; and, even in these cases, they are optimized on a single HPC center. Problems can arise due to HPC center policies, like the limitation of general connectivity from compute nodes.
 - **Status:** This should be resolved, but progress can be made in the interim.
 - **Impact:** The lack of outgoing connectivity from the worker nodes requires the development of entirely contained workflows and prevents the late scheduling of pilot-based workload management systems which dramatically lowers the efficiency. HPC facilities will be most beneficial to HEP when they can handle a significant fraction of the most processing intensive workflows. While some workflows can currently run on HPC, further development is needed to expand this list. Missing this, for example, when only limited types of workflows are executable, reflects into more difficult workload management decisions, and eventually into worse resource utilization.
 - **Possible Next Steps:** Work with experiments and the HPC Federation Initiatives to develop a consensus on selecting workflows that could be run on HPC resources, and assess the potential impact under the current provisioning, interfaces, software, and data/storage conditions. Identify the most limiting factors and study how resolving them would enhance the impact of HPC sites.

Authorization and Authentication

The LHC collaborations, with thousands of active users and large operations teams, rely on the “WLCG Trust” model. In this model, sites provide access to users and workflow sites depending on their membership in selected Virtual Organizations (VOs), which are certified via external services that authenticate and authorize interactions with local systems.

This approach simplifies user management but can pose challenges for HPC sites requiring stricter controls. For larger and more complex security demands, enhanced authentication services would be needed to satisfy site-specific requirements without compromising the flexibility and distributed nature of WLCG operations.

- **Open Issues:** The HPC sites lack a common federated system for authentication and authorization.
- **Status:** Individuals are authenticated with specific sites and authorized to perform tasks. There is no concept of a VO with members and different authorization levels, nor is there the concept of a role which might be mapped to a changing group of individuals.
- **Impact:** The situation can be tolerated but will limit the use of HPC sites to specific production workflows submitted by known individuals.
- **Possible Next Steps:**
 - **Developing an Access/Security Model:** There is a need for a security framework that adheres to national regulations while supporting the globally distributed nature of HEP collaborations. Regional projects like IRI and EFP can alleviate the problem, establishing a federated identity management which can be made interoperable with WLCG AAI.
 - **Federated Common Infrastructure:** Establishing a federated infrastructure is essential to facilitate collaboration across international sites and ensure secure, efficient resource sharing.
 - **AAI:** A federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure is the basis of all federated services. It should use industry standards in order to federate also external AAIs, in order to let a user authenticate on all/most sites with unique credentials.

Opportunities and Challenges of ML

AI and Machine Learning (ML) methods offer transformative opportunities for High Energy Physics (HEP), enabling innovative approaches to simulate, select, reconstruct, and analyze data. These techniques can significantly outperform traditional calculations, delivering greater efficiency and accelerating scientific discoveries.

The role of GPUs in machine learning (ML) applications is particularly crucial, attracting substantial industry investments. The focus on AI/ML offers new opportunities for HEP but potentially reduces some existing capabilities. In the push for faster AI processors, the industry has focused on lower precision calculations at the cost of improvements in the double precision calculations that HEP relies on for classical calculations. As this trend continues, each experiment will need to investigate which workflows can be refactored to look like AI/ML and which instead may need specialized high precision optimized hardware. These challenges emphasize the need for data intensive science and the HPC community to partner at the design phase to ensure the appropriate resources are available to meet the needs of applications.

Policies for Provisioning and Accounting

Large allocations of resources at HPC sites are generally awarded through peer-reviewed proposals and must be consumed within a year. In contrast, LHC experiments, with their multi-decade physics programs and long-term

computing requirements, favor multi-year allocations and guaranteed continuous site involvement via explicit MoUs with WLCG. Such allocations facilitate better resource planning and enable the experiments to secure resources that align with their long-term physics goals. Although LHC experiments invest in developing portable software that can be executed with minimal changes across various platforms, multi-year allocations (or at least annual “guaranteed” allocations) would allow them to capitalize on additional investments needed for specific HPC centers.

Applications identified as strategic science initiatives of the European Commission have consistent access to computing resources without being subject to an annual application process. HEP will respond more consistently to EuroHPC and national HPC access opportunities—including development, benchmarking, regular and extreme-scale access, AI, and data-intensive application calls—while building internal expertise to position HEP as a key candidate for “strategic access.”

Conclusions and Next Steps

The integration of High-Performance Computing (HPC) into the WLCG/HEP ecosystem holds immense potential for advancing the discovery reach of current and future particle physics experiments. By aligning on standard interfaces, modernizing software for heterogeneous architectures, establishing robust data pipelines, and collaborating on security and allocation policies, the community can capitalize on the power of exascale resources. This synergy between HPC centers and HEP collaborations is not only vital for tackling the data deluge of the HL-LHC era but also for sustaining a dynamic research environment where AI/ML techniques can thrive.

Moving forward, it will be critical to formalize co-design processes that consider HEP needs early in HPC design, ensuring that evolving architectures are suitable for large-scale data handling and specialized physics workflows. WLCG, and HPC facilities should jointly define a minimum set of standardized interfaces and security frameworks to facilitate seamless resource sharing. At the same time, multi-year allocation policies and strategic recognition of HEP’s unique requirements will enable experiments to leverage HPC resources effectively, while collaborating with existing programs like IRI, EuroHPC JU and EFP, and HPC resource providers. By fostering cross-disciplinary R&D initiatives—encompassing workload portability, workflow optimization, and federated identity management—the community can establish a sustainable model where HPC emerges as a cornerstone in the global effort to push the frontiers of high-energy physics.

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